

[Research Article]

Attitudes Towards and Willingness to Accept Malaria Vaccination among Caregivers of Under-Five Children in Plateau State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

Background:

Malaria remains a major public health challenge in Nigeria and contributes substantially to morbidity and mortality among children under five years of age. The recent introduction of malaria vaccines offers a promising addition to malaria control strategies. However, successful implementation depends on caregiver acceptance. This study assessed attitudes towards malaria vaccines and willingness to accept malaria vaccination among caregivers of under-five children in Plateau State, Nigeria.

Methods:

A community-based cross-sectional study was conducted among 408 caregivers of under-five children in selected communities in Plateau State, Nigeria. Participants were selected using a multistage sampling technique. Data were collected using a structured interviewer-administered questionnaire and analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 25. Descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, and multivariable logistic regression were used to identify factors associated with attitudes and willingness to accept malaria vaccination. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results:

Most caregivers (94.9%) demonstrated positive attitudes towards malaria vaccines, while 85.3% were willing to vaccinate their children. Although most recognized malaria as a serious health problem and vaccination as an important preventive strategy, concerns regarding vaccine side effects (91.1%), effectiveness (78.4%), and religious implications (87.8%) were common. Religion ($p = 0.008$), occupation ($p = 0.002$), educational status ($p < 0.001$), and family type ($p = 0.010$) were independently associated with attitudes towards malaria vaccines, while occupation was the only independent predictor of willingness to accept malaria vaccination ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusions:

Caregivers demonstrated positive attitudes towards malaria vaccines and a high willingness to vaccinate their children. However, concerns regarding vaccine safety, effectiveness, and religious implications remain. Strengthening community engagement and improving access to accurate vaccine information may enhance confidence and support successful malaria vaccine implementation.

Keywords: Malaria Vaccine, Vaccine Acceptance, Malaria prevention, Under-five children, Caregivers.

Introduction

Malaria remains one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality worldwide, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, where transmission is intense and children under five years bear the greatest burden of disease. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), an estimated 249 million malaria cases and 608,000 malaria-related deaths occurred globally in 2022, with approximately 95% of cases and deaths occurring in the African Region. Nigeria continues to carry the highest malaria burden worldwide, accounting for a substantial proportion of global malaria cases and deaths. Despite sustained implementation of malaria control interventions, including insecticide-treated nets (ITNs), indoor residual spraying (IRS), seasonal malaria chemoprevention, prompt diagnosis, and effective treatment, malaria transmission remains persistently high in many endemic communities, posing a major challenge to child survival and public health development (1–3).

The introduction of malaria vaccines represents a major milestone in global malaria prevention. Following decades of research, the RTS,S/AS01 vaccine became the first malaria vaccine recommended by the WHO for routine use among children living in areas of moderate-to-high malaria transmission in 2021 after demonstrating acceptable safety, efficacy, and public health impact in pilot implementation programmes (4,5). More recently, the R21/Matrix-M vaccine also received WHO recommendation after demonstrating high efficacy in Phase III clinical trials, providing an additional opportunity to strengthen malaria prevention strategies in endemic countries (6). Together with existing malaria control measures, these vaccines have the potential to substantially reduce malaria-related illness and mortality among African children.

However, the public health impact of malaria vaccination depends not only on vaccine availability but also on caregiver acceptance and demand. As primary decision-makers regarding childhood immunisation, caregivers play a pivotal role in determining whether eligible children receive recommended vaccines. Previous studies have consistently shown that confidence in vaccine safety,

trust in healthcare providers, perceived benefits of vaccination, and access to accurate health information are associated with greater vaccine acceptance. Conversely, concerns regarding adverse effects, doubts about vaccine effectiveness, misinformation, religious beliefs, and distrust of health systems contribute to vaccine hesitancy and lower vaccine uptake (7–12). Understanding caregivers' attitudes and willingness to accept malaria vaccination is therefore essential for ensuring successful implementation and long-term sustainability of malaria vaccination programmes.

Vaccine acceptance is a complex behavioural process influenced by multiple psychological, social, and contextual factors. The 3Cs Model of Vaccine Hesitancy, proposed by the WHO Strategic Advisory Group of Experts (SAGE), provides a useful framework for understanding vaccination behaviour by describing three key determinants: confidence (trust in vaccine safety, effectiveness, and the health system), complacency (perceived susceptibility to and severity of the disease), and convenience (accessibility, affordability, and availability of vaccination services). Within this framework, caregivers may generally support childhood vaccination while simultaneously expressing concerns about vaccine safety, effectiveness, or religious acceptability. Consequently, favourable overall attitudes do not necessarily eliminate specific concerns that may delay or discourage vaccine uptake. This conceptual framework provides an appropriate basis for interpreting attitudes and willingness to accept malaria vaccination in the present study.

Previous studies conducted in several African countries have generally reported favourable attitudes towards malaria vaccination while simultaneously identifying persistent concerns regarding vaccine safety, effectiveness, and possible adverse effects. In Kenya, caregiver acceptance of a prospective malaria vaccine was generally high, although acceptance varied according to educational level, satisfaction with healthcare services, and access to health information (13). Similarly, studies conducted in Ghana demonstrated high willingness among caregivers to vaccinate their children, while also highlighting the influence of awareness,

socioeconomic characteristics, and trust in health information on vaccine acceptance (14). More broadly, evidence from vaccine confidence studies across sub-Saharan Africa indicates that confidence in vaccines, trust in healthcare systems, and effective communication are among the strongest predictors of vaccine acceptance, whereas misinformation and safety concerns remain important barriers (7–12). Collectively, these findings suggest that vaccine acceptance should be viewed as a multidimensional construct rather than a simple dichotomy of acceptance versus refusal.

Although malaria vaccines represent a significant advancement in malaria prevention, evidence regarding caregiver attitudes and willingness to accept malaria vaccination in Nigeria remains limited, particularly during the early phase of malaria vaccine introduction. Most available Nigerian studies have focused on knowledge of malaria prevention or routine childhood immunisation, with comparatively few investigations examining caregiver attitudes towards malaria vaccines and the factors influencing vaccine acceptance. This evidence gap limits the ability of policymakers and programme implementers to design communication strategies that effectively address vaccine hesitancy and promote equitable vaccine uptake.

Plateau State, located in North-Central Nigeria, continues to experience substantial malaria transmission despite ongoing malaria control interventions. Understanding caregivers' attitudes, concerns, and willingness to accept malaria vaccination within this setting is therefore essential for informing context-specific implementation strategies, strengthening public confidence in malaria vaccination, and supporting successful programme rollout. Accordingly, this study assessed attitudes towards malaria vaccination and willingness to accept malaria vaccination among caregivers of under-five children in Plateau State, Nigeria, and examined selected sociodemographic factors associated with these outcomes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

This study was conducted in Plateau State, North-Central Nigeria. The state comprises 17 Local Government Areas (LGAs) with a mixture of urban, peri-urban, and rural communities. Plateau State experiences stable malaria transmission throughout the year, with increased transmission during the rainy season. Despite the implementation of malaria control interventions, including insecticide-treated nets, seasonal malaria chemoprevention, prompt diagnosis, and effective treatment, malaria remains a major cause of morbidity among children under five years of age. Variations in healthcare access, socioeconomic conditions, health-seeking behaviour, and utilization of childhood immunization services exist across the state, particularly between urban and rural communities (2,15).

Study Design and Population

A community-based cross-sectional study was conducted among caregivers of under-five children residing in selected communities in Plateau State, Nigeria. Caregivers were defined as parents or primary guardians responsible for making healthcare decisions for at least one child aged 0–59 months.

Eligible participants were caregivers aged 18 years or older who had resided in the selected communities for at least six months prior to data collection, had responsibility for the care of at least one child under five years of age, and provided written informed consent. Caregivers who were critically ill, temporary visitors to the community, or unable to complete the interview were excluded.

Sample Size Determination and Sampling Technique

The minimum sample size was determined using Cochran's formula for estimating a single population proportion based on the prevalence reported in a previous related study (14). The calculated sample size was adjusted for the multistage sampling design and anticipated non-response, resulting in a final sample size of 408 caregivers.

A multistage sampling technique was employed to recruit study participants. In the first stage, three LGAs representing urban, peri-urban, and rural settings were purposively selected to ensure geographical and socioeconomic representation

within Plateau State. Jos North represented the urban setting, Wase the peri-urban setting, and Kanam the rural setting.

In the second stage, one ward was selected from each LGA using simple random sampling by balloting. Subsequently, one community was randomly selected from each chosen ward using community administrative listings.

Households with eligible caregivers were identified through household enumeration conducted with the assistance of community leaders and primary healthcare workers. The required sample size was allocated proportionately to each selected community based on the estimated number of eligible households. Systematic random sampling was then employed to select households, with the sampling interval determined by dividing the total number of eligible households by the allocated sample size for each community (16). A random starting household was selected before every *k*th household was approached.

Where more than one eligible caregiver was identified within a household, one respondent was selected by simple random sampling through balloting. Households unavailable during the initial visit were revisited once before replacement with the next eligible household in the sampling sequence.

Data Collection Instrument

Data were collected using a structured interviewer-administered questionnaire developed following an extensive review of published literature on malaria vaccine acceptance, vaccine hesitancy, and childhood immunization (7–14). The questionnaire was adapted from previously validated instruments used to assess caregivers' attitudes and acceptance of malaria vaccination in African settings (13,14).

The questionnaire consisted of four sections:

1. Sociodemographic characteristics.
2. Attitudes towards malaria vaccination.
3. Willingness to accept malaria vaccination.
4. Vaccine-related perceptions, including perceived benefits, safety concerns, confidence in vaccine effectiveness, trust in healthcare providers,

religious beliefs, and exposure to vaccine-related information.

The questionnaire was reviewed independently by experts in public health, epidemiology, and community medicine to establish face and content validity. Suggestions provided during expert review were incorporated before field implementation.

Translation, Pretesting and Reliability Assessment

The questionnaire was translated from English into Hausa and independently back-translated into English to ensure conceptual equivalence and linguistic consistency.

A pretest was conducted among caregivers from a neighbouring Local Government Area that was not included in the main study. Feedback from the pilot survey was used to improve wording, clarity, sequence, cultural appropriateness, and comprehension of questionnaire items.

Internal consistency of the attitude scale was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, yielding a value of 0.81, indicating good internal reliability. A Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.70 or greater was considered acceptable (21).

Measurement of Attitudes towards Malaria Vaccination

Attitudes towards malaria vaccination were assessed using 12 statements measured on a five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). The statements assessed perceived severity of malaria, perceived benefits of malaria vaccination, vaccine safety, vaccine effectiveness, trust in healthcare workers, religious beliefs, and concerns regarding vaccination.

Negatively worded statements relating to vaccine safety, effectiveness, side effects, and religious concerns were reverse-coded before analysis to ensure that higher scores consistently represented more favorable attitudes towards malaria vaccination.

Composite attitude scores were calculated by summing responses across the 12 items, giving a possible score range of 12–60. Scores were converted into percentages and classified using the modified Bloom's cut-off criteria, where scores of 80–100%

were classified as positive attitudes, while scores below 80% were classified as negative attitudes (17,22,23). The modified Bloom's criteria have been widely applied in Knowledge, Attitude and Practice (KAP) studies to facilitate interpretation of composite attitude scores.

Measurement of Willingness to Accept Malaria Vaccination

Willingness to accept malaria vaccination was assessed using the question:

"If a malaria vaccine becomes available for your child, would you allow your child to receive it?"

Responses were categorized as willing or not willing. Respondents who indicated unwillingness were further asked to identify the principal reasons for their decision, including concerns regarding vaccine safety, vaccine effectiveness, possible adverse effects, misinformation, religious beliefs, or cultural considerations.

Data Collection Procedure

Data were collected through face-to-face household interviews conducted by trained research assistants. Training covered the study objectives, research ethics, informed consent procedures, interviewing techniques, questionnaire administration, and quality assurance measures.

Completed questionnaires were reviewed daily by field supervisors to ensure completeness, consistency, and accuracy. Any inconsistencies identified during field supervision were resolved through immediate verification where necessary.

Data Analysis

Data were entered, cleaned, and analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 25.

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize respondents' characteristics and study variables. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages, while continuous variables were summarized using means and standard deviations where appropriate.

Pearson's chi-square test was used to assess associations between independent variables and the

study outcomes. Variables that demonstrated statistical significance during bivariate analysis ($p < 0.05$), together with variables considered epidemiologically important based on previous literature, were entered into multivariable logistic regression models to identify independent predictors of positive attitudes towards malaria vaccination and willingness to accept malaria vaccination (18).

Adjusted odds ratios (aORs) with corresponding 95% confidence intervals (95% CIs) were reported. Statistical significance was established at $p < 0.05$.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Plateau State Health Research Ethics Committee. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants before enrolment. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were informed of their right to decline participation or withdraw from the study at any stage without consequences.

Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained throughout the study by removing personal identifiers from the study dataset. All procedures were conducted in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and its subsequent amendments (20).

RESULT

Sociodemographic Characteristics of Caregivers

As shown in Table 1, a total of 408 caregivers participated in the study. More than half of the respondents (56.1%) were older than 29 years, and the majority were female (76.7%). Slightly over half (52.9%) practiced Islam, while 47.1% were Christians.

Most caregivers were employed (56.4%) and had attained formal education (89.2%). The predominant ethnic group comprised Ngas, Berom, and other indigenous ethnicities (57.6%), whereas Hausa/Fulani respondents accounted for 42.4%. More than half of the respondents (55.9%) reported a monthly income of ₦70,000 or less, and most were married (91.9%). In addition, over half (55.6%) belonged to polygamous households, while nearly three-quarters (72.1%) had two or fewer children under five years of age.

Table 1. Sociodemographic Characteristics of Caregivers of Under-Five Children in Plateau State, Nigeria (N = 408)

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
≤29	179	43.9
>29	229	56.1
Sex		
Male	95	23.3
Female	313	76.7
Religion		
Islam	216	52.9
Christianity	192	47.1
Occupation		
Employed	230	56.4
Self-employed	178	43.6
Educational status		
Formal education	364	89.2
Non-formal education	44	10.8
Tribe/Ethnicity		
Hausa/Fulani	173	42.4
Ngas/Berom/Others	235	57.6
Monthly income (₦)		
≤70,000	228	55.9
>70,000	180	44.1
Marital status		

Married	375	91.9
Not married	33	8.1
Family type		
Monogamous	181	44.4
Polygamous	227	55.6
Number of under-five children		
≤2	294	72.1
>2	114	27.9

Attitudes Towards Malaria Vaccination Among Caregivers

Table 2. Distribution of Responses to Attitude Statements Towards Malaria Vaccination Among Caregivers of Under-Five Children in Plateau State, Nigeria (N = 408)

Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Malaria is a serious health problem in Plateau State		
Strongly Agree	360	88.2
Agree	44	10.8
Neutral	2	0.5
Disagree	2	0.5
Strongly Disagree	0	0.0
Malaria can result in death among children		
Strongly Agree	314	77.0
Agree	90	22.0
Neutral	4	1.0
Disagree	0	0.0
Strongly Disagree	0	0.0

Vaccines are generally safe for children under five years		
Strongly Agree	313	76.7
Agree	74	18.1
Neutral	9	2.2
Disagree	6	1.5
Strongly Disagree	6	1.5
It is important to vaccinate children against preventable diseases		
Strongly Agree	308	75.5
Agree	85	20.8
Neutral	9	2.2
Disagree	6	1.5
Strongly Disagree	0	0.0
If a malaria vaccine becomes available, I would trust it		
Strongly Agree	272	66.7
Agree	105	25.7
Neutral	29	7.1
Disagree	2	0.5
Strongly Disagree	0	0.0
I am concerned about the side effects of the malaria vaccine		
Strongly Agree	245	60.0
Agree	127	31.1
Neutral	26	6.4
Disagree	10	2.5

Strongly Disagree	0	0.0
I am concerned about the effectiveness of the malaria vaccine		
Strongly Agree	213	52.2
Agree	107	26.2
Neutral	79	19.4
Disagree	9	2.2
Strongly Disagree	0	0.0
I am concerned about the religious implications of the malaria vaccine		
Strongly Agree	254	62.3
Agree	104	25.5
Neutral	39	9.6
Disagree	4	1.0
Strongly Disagree	7	1.7
I feel comfortable discussing malaria vaccination with a health worker		
Strongly Agree	289	70.8
Agree	88	21.6
Neutral	25	6.1
Disagree	4	1.0
Strongly Disagree	2	0.5
I trust health workers regarding vaccines		
Strongly Agree	299	73.3
Agree	62	15.2
Neutral	43	10.5

Disagree	4	1.0
Strongly Disagree	0	0.0
I would follow a recommendation from religious leaders to vaccinate my child		
Strongly Agree	261	64.0
Agree	100	24.5
Neutral	33	8.1
Disagree	10	2.5
Strongly Disagree	4	1.0
Community campaigns on malaria vaccination are helpful		
Strongly Agree	301	73.8
Agree	86	21.1
Neutral	19	4.7
Disagree	2	0.5
Strongly Disagree	0	0.0

Table 2 presents caregivers' responses to individual attitude statements regarding malaria vaccination. Overall, respondents demonstrated favourable perceptions towards malaria and childhood vaccination. Nearly all caregivers agreed that malaria is a serious public health problem (99.0%) and that it can result in death among children (99.0%). Similarly, most respondents agreed that vaccines are generally safe for children (94.8%), acknowledged the importance of vaccinating children against preventable diseases (96.3%), and indicated that they would trust a malaria vaccine if it became available (92.4%).

Despite these favourable perceptions, important concerns regarding malaria vaccination remained evident. Approximately 91.1% of caregivers expressed concern about possible vaccine side effects, 78.4% questioned the effectiveness of the malaria vaccine, and 87.8% reported concerns regarding its religious implications. Nevertheless, confidence in healthcare providers remained high, with 88.5% reporting trust in health workers regarding vaccines, while 94.9% considered community awareness campaigns on malaria vaccination to be helpful.

These findings suggest that although caregivers generally viewed malaria vaccination positively, substantial concerns regarding vaccine safety, effectiveness, and religious acceptability persisted, indicating the presence of specific dimensions of vaccine hesitancy despite favourable overall attitudes.

Overall Attitude towards Malaria Vaccination

Table 3. Overall Composite Attitude towards Malaria Vaccination Among Caregivers of Under-Five Children in Plateau State, Nigeria (N = 408)

Attitude Category	Score (%) (<i>Equivalent Raw Score</i>)	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Positive attitude	80–100% (48–60 points)	387	94.9
Negative attitude	<80% (12–47 points)	21	5.1

Composite attitude scores were calculated from 12 Likert-scale items after reverse-coding negatively worded statements. Scores were converted to percentages and classified using the modified Bloom's cut-off criteria.

Table 3 summarizes caregivers' overall attitudes towards malaria vaccination based on the composite attitude score. Overall, 387 (94.9%) caregivers demonstrated a positive attitude towards malaria vaccination, whereas only 21 (5.1%) exhibited a negative attitude.

Willingness to Accept Malaria Vaccination

Table 4. Willingness to Accept Malaria Vaccination Among Caregivers of Under-Five Children in Plateau State, Nigeria (N = 408)

Response	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Yes	348	85.3
No	60	14.7

As presented in Table 4, the majority of caregivers (85.3%) expressed willingness to allow their under-five children to receive a malaria vaccine if it became available, whereas 14.7% indicated that they would not accept malaria vaccination for their children.

Factors Associated with Attitudes towards Malaria Vaccination

Table 5. Association between Sociodemographic Characteristics and Overall Attitudes Towards Malaria Vaccination Among Caregivers of Under-Five Children in Plateau State, Nigeria (N = 408)

Variable	Positive Attitude n (%)	Negative Attitude n (%)	χ^2	p-value
Age \leq 29 years	172 (96.1)	7 (3.9)	0.999	0.318
Age >29 years	215 (93.9)	14 (6.1)		
Female	300 (95.8)	13 (4.2)	2.719	0.099
Male	87 (91.6)	8 (8.4)		
Islam	199 (92.1)	17 (7.9)	6.973	0.008*
Christianity	188 (97.9)	4 (2.1)		

Employed	225 (97.8)	5 (2.2)	9.545	0.002*
Self-employed	162 (91.0)	16 (9.0)		
Formal education	353 (97.0)	11 (3.0)	31.221	<0.001*
Non-formal education	34 (77.3)	10 (22.7)		
Hausa/Fulani	160 (92.5)	13 (7.5)	3.448	0.063
Ngas/Berom/Others	227 (96.6)	8 (3.4)		
Monthly income ≤ ₦70,000	213 (93.4)	15 (6.6)	2.170	0.141
Monthly income > ₦70,000	174 (96.7)	6 (3.3)		
Married	356 (94.9)	19 (5.1)	0.061	0.804
Not married	31 (93.9)	2 (6.1)		
Monogamous family	166 (91.7)	15 (8.3)	6.571	0.010*
Polygamous family	221 (97.4)	6 (2.6)		
≤2 under-five children	281 (95.6)	13 (4.4)	1.134	0.287
>2 under-five children	106 (93.0)	8 (7.0)		

*Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Table 5 shows the association between caregivers' sociodemographic characteristics and overall attitudes towards malaria vaccination. At the bivariate level, religion, occupation, educational status, and family type were significantly associated with caregivers' attitudes towards malaria vaccination ($p < 0.05$).

Caregivers with formal education were significantly more likely to demonstrate positive attitudes than those with non-formal education (97.0% vs. 77.3%, $p < 0.001$). Similarly, employed caregivers exhibited more favourable attitudes than self-employed caregivers (97.8% vs. 91.0%, $p = 0.002$). Significant differences were also observed according to religious affiliation ($p = 0.008$) and family type ($p = 0.010$). However, no statistically significant associations were identified between overall attitude and respondents' age, sex, ethnicity, monthly income, marital status, or number of under-five children ($p > 0.05$).

Factors Associated with Willingness to Accept Malaria Vaccination

Table 6. Association between Sociodemographic Characteristics and Willingness to Accept Malaria Vaccination among Caregivers of Under-Five Children in Plateau State, Nigeria (N = 408)

Variable	Willing n (%)	Not Willing n (%)	χ^2	p-value
Age ≤29 years	159 (88.8)	20 (11.2)	3.173	0.075

Age >29 years	189 (82.5)	40 (17.5)		
Female	270 (86.3)	43 (13.7)	1.004	0.316
Male	78 (82.1)	17 (17.9)		
Islam	185 (85.6)	31 (14.4)	0.046	0.830
Christianity	163 (84.9)	29 (15.1)		
Employed	209 (90.9)	21 (9.1)	13.065	<0.001*
Self-employed	139 (78.1)	39 (21.9)		
Formal education	313 (86.0)	51 (14.0)	1.299	0.254
Non-formal education	35 (79.5)	9 (20.5)		
Hausa/Fulani	154 (89.0)	19 (11.0)	3.319	0.068
Ngas/Berom/Others	194 (82.6)	41 (17.4)		
Monthly income ≤ ₦70,000	192 (84.2)	36 (15.8)	0.484	0.487
Monthly income > ₦70,000	156 (86.7)	24 (13.3)		
Married	319 (85.1)	56 (14.9)	0.191	0.662
Not married	29 (87.9)	4 (12.1)		
Monogamous family	156 (86.2)	25 (13.8)	0.207	0.649
Polygamous family	192 (84.6)	35 (15.4)		
≤2 under-five children	252 (85.7)	42 (14.3)	0.148	0.700
>2 under-five children	96 (84.2)	18 (15.8)		

*Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

As presented in Table 6, occupation was the only sociodemographic characteristic significantly associated with willingness to accept malaria vaccination. Employed caregivers were significantly more willing to vaccinate their children than self-employed caregivers (90.9% vs. 78.1%, $p < 0.001$).

No statistically significant associations were observed between willingness to accept malaria vaccination and age, sex, religion, educational status, ethnicity, monthly income, marital status, family type, or the number of under-five children ($p > 0.05$).

Multivariable Logistic Regression Analysis of Predictors of Attitudes Towards Malaria Vaccination

Table 7. Multivariable Logistic Regression Analysis of Predictors of Negative Attitudes Towards Malaria Vaccination Among Caregivers of Under-Five Children in Plateau State, Nigeria (N = 408)

Variable	AOR	95% CI	p-value
Religion			
Islam	4.02	1.33–12.15	0.014*
Christianity	1.00	Reference	
Occupation			
Employed	0.23	0.08–0.63	0.004*
Self-employed	1.00	Reference	
Educational Status			
Formal education	0.11	0.04–0.27	<0.001*
Non-formal education	1.00	Reference	
Family Type			
Polygamous	0.30	0.11–0.79	0.015*
Monogamous	1.00	Reference	

Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Variables that demonstrated statistical significance during the bivariate analysis were entered into a multivariable logistic regression model to identify independent predictors of negative attitudes towards malaria vaccination. After adjustment for potential confounding variables, religion, occupation, educational status, and family type remained independently associated with caregivers' attitudes.

Muslim caregivers had significantly higher odds of exhibiting negative attitudes towards malaria vaccination compared with Christian caregivers (aOR = 4.02; 95% CI: 1.33–12.15; $p = 0.014$). Conversely, employed caregivers had 77% lower odds of demonstrating negative attitudes than self-employed caregivers (aOR = 0.23; 95% CI: 0.08–0.63; $p = 0.004$).

Similarly, caregivers with formal education had significantly lower odds of negative attitudes than those with non-formal education (aOR = 0.11; 95% CI: 0.04–0.27; $p < 0.001$). In addition, caregivers from polygamous households had lower odds of negative attitudes than those from monogamous households (aOR = 0.30; 95% CI: 0.11–0.79; $p = 0.015$).

Multivariable Logistic Regression Analysis of Predictors of Willingness to Accept Malaria Vaccination

Table 8. Multivariable Logistic Regression Analysis of Predictors of Willingness to Accept Malaria Vaccination Among Caregivers of Under-Five Children in Plateau State, Nigeria (N = 408)

Variable	AOR	95% CI	p-value
Occupation			
Unemployed/Self-employed	0.35	0.20–0.63	<0.001*
Employed	1.00	Reference	
Religion			
Islam	0.85	0.47–1.52	0.579
Christianity	1.00	Reference	
Educational Status			
Formal education	0.56	0.24–1.31	0.182
Non-formal education	1.00	Reference	

*Statistically significant; AOR, Adjusted odds ratio; CI=Confidence interval.

A multivariable logistic regression model was fitted to identify independent predictors of caregivers' willingness to accept malaria vaccination. After adjustment for potential confounding variables, occupation remained the only significant independent predictor of willingness to vaccinate.

Caregivers who were self-employed or unemployed had significantly lower odds of accepting malaria vaccination for their children than employed caregivers (aOR = 0.35; 95% CI: 0.20–0.63; $p < 0.001$). Religion and educational status were not independently associated with willingness to accept malaria vaccination after adjustment for other covariates ($p > 0.05$).

Discussion

This study assessed caregivers' attitudes towards malaria vaccination and their willingness to accept malaria vaccination for under-five children in Plateau State, Nigeria. Overall, caregivers demonstrated favorable attitudes towards malaria vaccination and a high willingness to vaccinate their children. However, despite these encouraging findings, substantial concerns regarding vaccine side effects, effectiveness, and religious implications were also identified. These findings suggest that caregiver attitudes towards malaria vaccination are multidimensional and that positive overall perceptions may coexist with specific concerns capable of influencing vaccination decisions.

The study found that nearly all caregivers recognized malaria as a serious public health problem and

acknowledged its potential to cause severe illness and death among young children. Most respondents also considered childhood vaccination to be an important preventive intervention and expressed confidence in malaria vaccination should it become available. These findings are consistent with studies conducted in malaria-endemic countries, where caregivers generally recognize the burden of malaria and perceive vaccination as an important strategy for protecting children against the disease (7–9,12–14). Given the persistent malaria burden in Nigeria, repeated exposure to malaria-related illness may have increased caregivers' perceived susceptibility to the disease and strengthened their support for preventive interventions such as vaccination.

An important finding of this study was the apparent discrepancy between the overall composite attitude score and responses to individual attitude statements.

Although most caregivers were classified as having positive attitudes towards malaria vaccination, large proportions also expressed concerns regarding vaccine side effects, effectiveness, and religious implications. Rather than representing contradictory findings, this pattern reflects the complexity of vaccine acceptance behaviour. The composite attitude score summarized caregivers' overall perceptions across multiple domains after reverse-coding negatively worded items, whereas individual questions captured specific concerns that may persist despite generally favorable attitudes. Similar findings have been reported in vaccine confidence research, where individuals often support vaccination while simultaneously expressing concerns regarding vaccine safety, effectiveness, or potential adverse events (7,8,12). Within the WHO Strategic Advisory Group of Experts (SAGE) 3Cs Model of Vaccine Hesitancy, these concerns primarily reflect issues of confidence, which refers to trust in vaccines, healthcare providers, and immunization programmes. Consequently, favorable overall attitudes should not be interpreted as the complete absence of vaccine hesitancy but rather as evidence that specific concerns require targeted communication and reassurance.

The study further demonstrated that 85.3% of caregivers were willing to allow their children to receive malaria vaccination if it became available. This high level of stated willingness is encouraging and is broadly consistent with previous studies conducted in sub-Saharan Africa, where caregivers generally express support for malaria vaccination during the pre-implementation phase (13,14). Nevertheless, willingness measured in cross-sectional surveys reflects behavioral intention rather than actual vaccination behaviour. Evidence from behavioural science indicates that intention does not always translate into vaccine uptake, particularly when concerns regarding vaccine safety, effectiveness, accessibility, or misinformation remain unresolved. Therefore, although the findings suggest favourable acceptance of malaria vaccination, successful programme implementation will depend on sustained public engagement and effective communication strategies that address caregivers' specific concerns. Trust in healthcare workers

emerged as another important finding of this study. Most caregivers reported confidence in healthcare providers and indicated that they would feel comfortable discussing malaria vaccination with health professionals. This observation is consistent with previous studies demonstrating that healthcare workers remain among the most trusted sources of vaccine-related information and play a central role in influencing vaccination decisions (7,12). Strengthening the capacity of healthcare providers to communicate accurate, evidence-based information regarding malaria vaccine safety, effectiveness, eligibility, and expected adverse events may therefore improve vaccine confidence and facilitate successful programme implementation.

Educational attainment was independently associated with caregivers' attitudes towards malaria vaccination. Caregivers with formal education were significantly more likely to demonstrate favourable attitudes than those without formal education. Similar associations have been reported in studies examining vaccine acceptance and health-seeking behaviour, where education improves health literacy, facilitates access to reliable health information, and enhances the ability to evaluate vaccine-related messages critically (8,9,18). These findings suggest that communication strategies should be tailored to caregivers with lower educational attainment using culturally appropriate and easily understandable messages. Occupation was also independently associated with both attitudes towards malaria vaccination and willingness to accept vaccination. Employed caregivers were more likely to demonstrate favourable attitudes and greater willingness to vaccinate their children than self-employed caregivers. Comparable findings have been reported in studies examining childhood immunization and vaccine acceptance, where socioeconomic characteristics influence access to healthcare services, exposure to health information, and opportunities for interaction with healthcare providers (18,20). These findings highlight the need to ensure that malaria vaccine communication strategies effectively reach caregivers across different occupational and socioeconomic groups.

Religious affiliation was significantly associated with caregivers' attitudes towards malaria vaccination. In

addition, many respondents reported that recommendations from religious leaders could influence their vaccination decisions. Previous studies have demonstrated that religious institutions and faith leaders frequently influence community attitudes towards vaccination through trusted social networks and established community structures (8,12). Consequently, engaging religious leaders during malaria vaccine introduction may strengthen public confidence, address misconceptions, and improve community acceptance of malaria vaccination programmes. Family type also emerged as an independent predictor of attitudes towards malaria vaccination. Although evidence specifically linking family structure to malaria vaccine acceptance remains limited, previous studies suggest that household decision-making processes, family dynamics, and social support influence preventive health behaviours, including childhood immunization. Further research is required to better understand the mechanisms through which family structure influences caregivers' perceptions and vaccination decisions.

The findings of this study have important implications for malaria vaccine implementation in Nigeria. Although caregivers generally demonstrated favorable attitudes and high willingness to accept malaria vaccination, substantial concerns regarding vaccine safety, effectiveness, and religious acceptability remained evident. These concerns should not be interpreted as opposition to vaccination but rather as opportunities for targeted risk communication and community engagement. Public health programmes should prioritize transparent communication regarding vaccine safety and effectiveness, strengthen healthcare worker training in vaccine communication, and actively involve community and religious leaders in malaria vaccine advocacy. Addressing these concerns before and during programme implementation may enhance public confidence and improve vaccine uptake.

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the findings. First, the cross-sectional design precludes causal inference and limits interpretation to observed associations between study variables. Second, the study relied on self-reported responses and may therefore be subject to

recall bias and social desirability bias. Third, willingness to accept malaria vaccination was assessed as a stated intention rather than actual vaccination behaviour, and intentions may not necessarily translate into future vaccine uptake. Fourth, the study was conducted in selected communities within Plateau State and may not fully represent caregiver perceptions in other regions of Nigeria. Nevertheless, the inclusion of urban, peri-urban, and rural populations enhances the contextual relevance of the findings and provides useful insights for similar malaria-endemic settings. Finally, the study was conducted during the early phase of malaria vaccine introduction, when public awareness and understanding of malaria vaccination were still evolving, which may have influenced caregiver perceptions and responses.

Conclusion

This study assessed attitudes towards malaria vaccination and willingness to accept malaria vaccination among caregivers of under-five children in Plateau State, Nigeria. Overall, caregivers demonstrated favorable attitudes towards malaria vaccination and a high stated willingness to vaccinate their children should a malaria vaccine become available. Most respondents recognized malaria as a serious public health problem and acknowledged the importance of vaccination as a strategy for preventing malaria-related illness among children. Despite these favorable overall attitudes, substantial concerns regarding vaccine safety, effectiveness, and religious implications were also identified. These findings indicate that positive overall attitudes towards malaria vaccination may coexist with specific concerns that reflect important dimensions of vaccine hesitancy. Consequently, successful malaria vaccine implementation will depend not only on vaccine availability but also on effective communication strategies that strengthen public confidence and address caregivers' concerns.

Educational status, occupation, religion, and family type were independently associated with caregivers' attitudes towards malaria vaccination, while occupation emerged as the only independent predictor of willingness to accept malaria vaccination. These findings identify important

population groups that may benefit from targeted communication and community engagement strategies. Overall, the findings suggest that strengthening caregiver education, promoting accurate and transparent information on malaria vaccine safety and effectiveness, and engaging trusted healthcare workers, community leaders, and religious leaders may enhance public confidence and support successful implementation of malaria vaccination programmes in Plateau State and similar settings.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Public Health Authorities and Policy Makers

Public health authorities should integrate malaria vaccine communication into existing malaria control and routine immunization programmes. Communication strategies should provide clear, evidence-based information regarding vaccine safety, effectiveness, expected adverse events, and the continued importance of complementary malaria prevention measures to improve public confidence and address vaccine-related concerns.

Healthcare Workers

Healthcare workers should receive regular training on malaria vaccines, vaccine safety, and effective risk communication to strengthen their capacity to respond to caregivers' questions and concerns. Given the high level of trust reported in healthcare providers, they should play a central role in promoting informed decision-making and vaccine confidence.

Community and Religious Leaders

Community leaders, religious leaders, and other trusted local stakeholders should be actively involved in community sensitization and vaccine advocacy activities. Their engagement may help address misconceptions, improve confidence in malaria vaccination, and encourage community acceptance during programme implementation.

Health Education and Communication

Targeted health education programmes should be developed for caregivers with lower educational attainment and those with limited access to reliable

health information. Educational materials should be culturally appropriate, easy to understand, and delivered through multiple communication channels, including primary healthcare facilities, community outreach activities, mass media, and local religious institutions.

Future Research

Future studies should include multiple states and geopolitical zones of Nigeria to improve the generalizability of findings and examine regional differences in caregivers' attitudes and willingness to accept malaria vaccination. Prospective implementation and longitudinal studies are also recommended following large-scale malaria vaccine introduction to evaluate actual vaccine uptake, identify barriers and facilitators to vaccination, and assess the effectiveness of communication and community engagement strategies over time.

ETHICS STATEMENT

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Plateau State Health Research Ethics Committee. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection. Participation was voluntary, and confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained throughout the study. The study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

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COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The datasets generated and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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ABBREVIATIONS

WHO – World Health Organization

ITNs – Insecticide-Treated Nets

IRS – Indoor Residual Spraying

RTS,S – RTS,S/AS01 Malaria Vaccine

R21 – R21/Matrix-M Malaria Vaccine

LGA – Local Government Area

aOR – Adjusted Odds Ratio

CI – Confidence Interval

SPSS – Statistical Package for the Social Sciences

NMEP – National Malaria Elimination Programme

References

1. World Health Organization. World malaria report 2023. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2023.
2. National Malaria Elimination Programme, National Population Commission, National Bureau of Statistics, ICF. Nigeria malaria indicator survey 2021 final report. Abuja, Nigeria; 2022.
3. World Health Organization. Global technical strategy for malaria 2016–2030: 2021 update. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2021.
4. RTS,S Clinical Trials Partnership, Agnandji ST, Lell B, Fernandes JF, Abossolo BP, Methogo BG, et al. A phase 3 trial of RTS,S/AS01 malaria vaccine in African infants and children. *N Engl J Med*. 2015;372(24):2284–95. doi:10.1056/NEJMoa1505819.
5. World Health Organization. WHO recommends groundbreaking malaria vaccine for children at risk. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2021.
6. Dattoo MS, Natama HM, Somé A, Traoré O, Rouamba T, Bellamy D, et al. Efficacy of a low-dose candidate R21/Matrix-M malaria vaccine with seasonal administration to children in Burkina Faso: a randomised controlled trial. *Lancet*. 2021;397(10287):1809–18. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(21)00943-0.
7. Larson HJ, Jarrett C, Eckersberger E, Smith DMD, Paterson P. Understanding vaccine hesitancy around vaccines and vaccination from a global perspective: A systematic review of published literature, 2007–2012. *Vaccine*. 2014;32(19):2150–9.
8. MacDonald NE; SAGE Working Group on Vaccine Hesitancy. Vaccine hesitancy: Definition, scope and determinants. *Vaccine*. 2015;33(34):4161–4. doi:10.1016/j.vaccine.2015.04.036.
9. Oduwole EO, Pienaar ED, Mahomed H, Wiysonge CS. Vaccine hesitancy among caregivers in Nigeria: A systematic review. *Vaccine*. 2021;39(37):5298–305.
10. Brewer NT, Chapman GB, Rothman AJ, Leask J, Kempe A. Increasing vaccination: Putting psychological science into action. *Lancet*. 2017;390(10108):2252–72.
11. Otieno NA, Nyawanda BO, Adhiambo B, Akinyi P, Wanjala S, Ochieng J, et al. Caregiver acceptance of RTS,S malaria vaccine in Kenya: A cross-sectional study. *Vaccine*. 2022;40(9):1320–7.
12. Adjei G, Boahen O, Owusu R, Asante KP, Owusu-Agyei S, Agyeman-Duah J. Caregiver perceptions and acceptance of malaria vaccine implementation in Ghana. *BMC Health Serv Res*. 2021;21:404.
13. World Health Organization. Behavioural and social drivers of vaccination: Tools and practical guidance for achieving high uptake. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2022.
14. Plateau State Ministry of Health. Plateau State malaria situation report. Jos: Plateau State Ministry of Health; 2022.

15. Cochran WG. Sampling techniques. 3rd ed. New York: John Wiley & Sons; 1977.
16. United Nations Children's Fund. Community engagement for immunization programmes. New York: UNICEF; 2021.
17. Obasi CN, Ekwueme O, Agu AP, Onwasigwe CN, Uzochukwu BSC, Onoka CA. Socioeconomic determinants of vaccine acceptance in Nigeria. *Pan Afr Med J.* 2020;35:118.
18. Kaindoa EW, Mkude S, Ngowo HS, Finda M, Okumu FO, Ferguson HM. Sociodemographic determinants of malaria vaccine willingness in Tanzania. *Vaccine.* 2019;37(8):1209–16.
19. Cronbach LJ. Coefficient alpha and the internal structure of tests. *Psychometrika.* 1951;16(3):297–334.
20. Bloom BS. Taxonomy of educational objectives: Handbook I: Cognitive domain. New York: David McKay; 1956.
21. Kaliyaperumal K. Guideline for conducting a Knowledge, Attitude and Practice (KAP) study. *AECS Illumination.* 2004;4(1):7–9.
22. World Medical Association. World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki: Ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects. *JAMA.* 2013;310(20):2191–4.